

Sensitive dependency of minimum spouting velocity on angle of repose of solid particles and cone angle in conical spouted beds

Palash Kumar Mollick^{a,b,c,*}, Mikel Tellabide^a, Maider Bolaños^a, Idoia Estiati^a, Xabier Sukunza^a, Martin Olazar^{a,**}

^a Department of Chemical Engineering, University of the Basque Country, UPV/EHU, Leioa, Spain

^b Glass & Advanced Materials Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai, India

^c Faculty of Engineering Science, Homi Bhabha National Institute, Mumbai, India

HIGHLIGHTS

- The effect of angle of repose has been analysed in conical spouted beds.
- Angle of repose shows a great influence on the minimum spouting velocity.
- Minimum spouting velocity and stable pressure drop supports the findings.
- A critical transition of contactor angle happens at different angles of repose.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Spouted bed
Hydrodynamics
Minimum spouting velocity
Conical angle
Angle of repose

ABSTRACT

Minimum spouting velocity (u_{ms}) varies with the geometry of a Spouted Bed (SB) contactor and the gas-solid properties. The angle of repose (θ_r), being an important bulk property of the solid granules, is found to play a critical role causing the variation of u_{ms} with a change in contactor angle (γ_c). A systematic experimental study was conducted considering three different types of solid particles having significantly different θ_r (25° , 36° & 45°) and three different γ_c (28° , 45° & 60°) for three different gas inlet diameters, to evaluate u_{ms} and bed pressure drop (ΔP_b). The variation of u_{ms} is correlated with $(\tan \gamma_c/2)$ and it is found to have three distinct zones for different θ_r for which exponent over $(\tan \gamma_c/2)$, E , is highly affected making a significant change in u_{ms} .

* Corresponding author at: Department of Chemical Engineering, University of the Basque Country, UPV/EHU, Leioa, Spain.

** Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: palashkumar.mollick@ehu.eus, pmollick@barc.gov.in (P.K. Mollick), martin.olazar@ehu.eus (M. Olazar).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2024.119504>

Received 10 October 2023; Received in revised form 11 December 2023; Accepted 4 February 2024

Available online 6 February 2024

0032-5910/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Fig. 1. Particles of different angle of repose used in this study. Schematic showing “fixed funnel method” used to determine θ_r in the present study.

1. Introduction

The Spouted Bed (SB) is a solid and fluid contactor especially used for Geldart’s D-type particles [1]. Over the time, it has received adequate interests for its simple design aspects and thus easy maintenance during its industrial use in plant scale. Due to the stated reason, SB is widely used for drying of food grains or nuts [2–4], coating over pharmaceutical products or nuclear fuel or functional materials [5–8], gasification of biomass or waste, pyrolysis for depolymerisation leading to massive use in green energy sectors [9–14].

The minimum spouting velocity (u_{ms}) is the minimum required superficial fluid velocity, U , (measured at the inlet orifice below the bed) to maintain a sustainable spout zone in a spouted bed. u_{ms} can be obtained experimentally for a given solid-fluid system and the contactor geometry [15–20]. SB has a unique hydrodynamic feature differing from that of a conventional fluidized bed. Thus, operation of a SB is slightly critical and need a pre-calculation of u_{ms} if the experimental data is not available for a given fluid-solid system and the contactor geometry [21–26].

It has been well identified by previous studies that apart from the density (ρ_p) and size (d_p) of the particles, as well as the density and viscosity of the spouting fluid, the major influencing parameters on u_{ms} are the static bed height (H_0), top and bottom diameters of the conical section of the contactor (D_c and D_i respectively), cone angle (γ_c) and gas inlet diameter (D_o) [27–32]. However, majority of the earlier reports agree well with the variation of u_{ms} with the static bed height and gas inlet diameter for similar density of particles [33–35]. Many other results also confirm the dependency of u_{ms} with *Archemedes number* (which essentially contains the density and size of the particles and density and viscosity of the spouting fluid) almost in a very similar manner [30,34,36]. D_i/D_c , which essentially indicates γ_c , is invariably found to change in almost linear manner with u_{ms} . Thus, as D_i/D_c is increased Re_{ms} is found to decrease. Hosseini et al., who are a leading group in these types of contactors, proved the dependency of u_{ms} with D_i , D_o & D_c [36–42]. A great ambiguity still remains unsettled for the case of true dependency of u_{ms} with γ_c and D_c , which at times has been considered intrinsically with the former one without explicit consideration [27,29,31–36,43].

Therefore, in the present study, we aim to find out u_{ms} and the corresponding bed pressure drop (ΔP_b) for different contactor angles using different particles having different flowability index in terms of angle of repose (θ_r). This angle largely depends on the surface roughness of the particles and their shape. For the first time, here we attempt to report the influence of θ_r of the particle on deciding γ_c and thus u_{ms} . The result shows a crispy idea to decide the contactor angle for a specific particulate bed to attain benefit in terms of lower bed pressure drop as well as u_{ms} .

2. Experimental

2.1. Material

Three types of solid particles have been used in this study. They were chosen in such a way that the average ρ_p and d_p of those particles be very

Table 1
Properties of particles.

Materials	Size, average d_p , (mm)	Density, (kg/m ³)	Φ , (-)	θ_r , (°)
Pulse	3.4	1230	0.7	25 ± 1
Poly Ethylene (PE)	3.5	1400	0.7	36 ± 1
Rice	3.0	1250	0.6	45 ± 1

Fig. 2. Schematic of the spouted bed contactor.

close to each other. At the same time, those particles have significant variation in θ_r . Fig. 1 shows a photograph of the particles used in the present study. I) Pulse grain, which is a highly flowable having low $\theta_r = 25^\circ$. II) Poly Ethylene (PE) beads are moderately flowable with $\theta_r = 36^\circ$ and III) Rice grain poorly flowable with high $\theta_r = 45^\circ$. Particle properties are listed in Table 1. The average size of the particles (d_p) was determined using sieving and image processing (Image Pro Plus®). The apparent density (ρ_p) was determined based on the displacement method using toluene. Sphericity (Φ) was determined according to the method proposed by Zenz and Othmer (1960) (the surface of a sphere with the same volume of the particle over the surface of the particle).

The θ_r was measured using the conventional “fixed funnel method” for all the particles used here. In this method, particles are poured through a funnel to make a pile with a pre-determined width, as depicted in the schematic (Fig. 1). The angle made between the flat surface and the surface of the pile is the θ_r .

Fig. 3. (a) Photograph of the SB contactors used in the present study.
(b) Photograph of the cross section of the gas inlet used in the present study.

2.2. Geometry

Fig. 2 shows a schematic of the SB contactor having a conical angle γ_c . D_c and D_i are the top and bottom diameters of the conical section respectively, whereas, D_o is the diameter of the fluid inlet. H_0 is the static height of the particulate bed. Fig. 3 (a) shows a photograph of the actual SB contactors used in the present study. The photograph of the cross section of the gas inlets is given in Fig. 3 (b).

3. Method

Systematic experiments were performed using three different particles and three difference contactors as mentioned above. Measured amount corresponds to the pre-decided static bed height (H_0 - 0.2 m), with the solid bed being charged from the top of the contactor every time for each experiment, where air was used as the spouting gas. Air was pumped through a centralized air compressor (capacity of 5.5 kW) and its flow rate was measured digitally by a mass flow controller (Eldridge Products. Inc., model-440, range of 0–2 bar). The minimum spouting flow rate was measured during the decreasing flow rate condition as a standard practice to determine the u_{ms} . Minimum spouting flow rate was measured each time for a change of bed materials (for θ_r), SB contactors (for γ_c) and gas inlets (D_o). The corresponding ΔP_b was noted from a digital differential pressure transducer (Endress+Hauser, model-PMD55B, range of 0-16 MPa).

All the data points correspond to the average value of a minimum three number of experiments with a deviation below 5%.

4. Results and discussions

4.1. Effect on u_{ms}

Fig. 4a, b and c show the changes in u_{ms} with γ_c for three different particles having different θ_r at a fixed static height of the bed (H_0) of 0.2 m and gas inlet diameters (D_o) of 0.03, 0.04 and 0.05 m respectively. It is clearly observable that u_{ms} increases very linearly with the increase in γ_c for all types of particles having different θ_r . This happens due to the obvious reason of increased bed volume and hence the bed mass as well, for the higher γ_c , while maintaining a fixed H_0 . Interestingly, slopes for all the trend lines are different and inversely varying with the corresponding θ_r , as can be seen in Fig. 5. In the other term, the rate (sensitivity) of change of u_{ms} with γ_c is inversely proportional to the corresponding θ_r .

4.2. Effect on ΔP_b

Fig. 6 a, b and c show the changes in ΔP_b with γ_c for three different particles having different θ_r at a fixed static height of the bed (H_0) of 0.2 m and gas inlet diameters (D_o) of 0.03, 0.04 and 0.05 m, respectively. It is clearly seen that ΔP_b is increasing with γ_c , which is expected owing to the fact that the mass of the bed is increasing with γ_c . It is interesting to note that ΔP_b is higher as γ_c is increased, with this trend being more significant for the lower θ_r with smaller D_o . This implies, ΔP_b is higher as the particulate matter is more flowable. The actual photographs of the bed characteristics, as shown in Fig. 7, may explained the reason for this fact. The photographs of the bed were taken from the top while maintaining spouting velocity at $\sim 1.1u_{ms}$. Schematic in the inset of the photograph (Fig. 7) shows apparent bed surface characteristics from the side view. For the more flowable particulate matter ($\theta_r = 25^\circ$), the annular zone is seen to be quite expanded, making the bed in a dome shaped (Fig. 7a). This happens due to loosely bound particulate matter in the annular zone, which allows more gas to pass thorough it without contributing to the spout. Nevertheless, a major portion of the gas does not pass through the annular zone of the particulate bed having lower flowability ($\theta_r = 45^\circ$), making the bed slightly shrunk towards the spout zone, as seen in Fig. 7b. This fact is also supported by the higher u_{ms} (as shown in Fig. 4). For the lower D_o , volume of the annular zone is expected to be higher and thus an additional amount of gas passes through the annulus increasing both u_{ms} and ΔP_b .

If we compare Fig. 6a, b & c, it is evident that ΔP_b is lower for the higher D_o irrespective of θ_r . In fact, at the highest D_o studied here, ΔP_b does not change significantly and also shows almost unchanged value with increasing γ_c for the case of the higher θ_r values (36° and 45° , in this study). This happens at a high D_o (or D_o/D_i ratio) due to the interlocking of irregular particles or particles having rough surface (less flowable) resting in the annular region, which is enhanced by higher γ_c . In the other term, at a lower D_o (or D_o/D_i ratio) with lower θ_r , particles have higher tendency to enter into the spout zone from the annulus crossing the spout-annular interface (without resting in the annular zone) causing higher ΔP_b . For this reason, a preferred channelling with a fluctuation in movement of the spout region is observed in the case of rice particles ($\theta_r = 45^\circ$ at $\gamma_c = 60^\circ$), as shown in Fig. 7d, with almost flat bed surface on the annulus, with minor wavy texture. Furthermore, a detailed observation reveals that the diameter of the spout is smaller for the particles with higher θ_r . It means, the bed in the annular zone is rather rigid, thus hindering particles to move from annulus into spout zone.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4. Evolution of u_{ms} with γ_c for different θ_r at a fixed H_0 of 0.2 m and at D_o (a) 0.03, (b) 0.04 and (c) 0.05 m, respectively.

4.3. Interdependency of θ_r and γ_c

Let us express the dependency of u_{ms} with θ_r and γ_c in the form of an equation given below:

$$u_{ms} \propto (\tan \gamma_c / 2)^\epsilon \tag{1}$$

where “ ϵ ” is the exponent over $(\tan \gamma_c / 2)$. The plot in Fig. 8 shows

Fig. 5. Change of slope (u_{ms} / γ_c) corresponding to θ_r at different D_o .

the dependency of ϵ on θ_r .

The value of the exponent ϵ is found to increase nearly from 0.5 to 1.0, when θ_r is increased.

from 25 to 36°. This implies the dependency of U_{ms} on $\tan \gamma_c / 2$ increases with increase in θ_r .

from 25 to 36°. Tsvik et al. (1967) [34] had reported a similar value of 0.42, with the the solid being fertilizer granules (urea, which has a typical $\theta_r < 30^\circ$). Zhou et al. (2012) [43] and Golshan et al. (2018) [33] had reported the value of ϵ to be 0.87 and 0.78, respectively, using zirconia particles in both cases ($\theta_r \sim 33\text{--}35^\circ$). Hence, the present results are consistent with previously reported ones. Thus, the value of the exponent ϵ falls down to nearly 0.5 with a further increase in θ_r from 36 to 45°. This fact may be due to the higher chances of resting in the annular zone for irregular particles without entraining into the spout zone through the annular-spout interface. This is also evident by the pressure drop data presented above. As can be seen, even though γ_c increases (and so the mass of solid within the bed), pressure drop is seen to be almost unchanged for the higher D_o/D_i ratio. Rocha et al. (1995) reported the value of ϵ is 0.06 when used inert tablets, as this solid is expected to have very high $\theta_r (>45^\circ)$. Theoretically, if we extrapolate the trend, it may appear that the ϵ becomes zero for a very high θ_r .

5. Conclusions

In the past, eminent researchers have reported the change in the minimum spouting velocity (u_{ms}) with the contactor angle (γ_c). Many of them have found that γ_c bears a positive exponent to alter u_{ms} . Nevertheless, the reported values of the exponent seem to vary depending on the angle of the conical bed and particle type. Here, we report for the first time the variation of u_{ms} with the combined effect of γ_c and θ_r (a bulk property of the solid).

Similar to the earlier reports, it is found that the minimum spouting velocity (u_{ms}) proportionally varies with the contactor angle (γ_c) and can be expressed as $u_{ms} \propto (\tan \gamma_c / 2)^\epsilon$, with a positive value of ϵ . However, the degree of variation of u_{ms} with γ_c is dramatically dependent on the angle of repose (θ_r) of the particulate bed. Within the scope of our study, it is found that the ϵ may be considered as 1.0 when θ_r is very close to 35° (moderately flowable particulate matter). Nevertheless, one can consider this value as 0.5 when $\theta_r < 25^\circ$ (highly flowable particles). The value of ϵ can also be considered as 0.5 or further low if $\theta_r > 45^\circ$ (poorly flowable particulates).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Palash Kumar Mollick: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Mikel Tellabide:** Data curation, Methodology,

Fig. 6. Evolution of ΔP_b with γ_c for different θ_r at a fixed H_0 of 0.2 m and at D_o (a) 0.03, (b) 0.04 and (c) 0.05 m respectively.

Resources. **Maidier Bolaños:** Methodology, Validation. **Idoia Estiati:** Formal analysis, Validation. **Xabier Sukunza:** Methodology, Software. **Martin Olazar:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

Fig. 7. Photograph of top view of the spouted bed at $\sim 1.1 u_{ms}$ for different θ_r and γ_c with $D_o = 0.04$ m. Inset (blue line) present a general texture of bed as can be seen from side. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. Change of ϵ with θ_r at different D_o/D_i .

the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

The Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Postdoctoral Fellowships carried out this work with the financial support for Palash Kumar Mollick through the grant PROSPER-GAP-101061987 by European Commission. A partial financial support has been received from the grant PID2022-139454OB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and the grants IT1645-22 and KK-2023/00060 funded by the Basque Government. Maidier Bolaños thanks the University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU for her Ph.D. grant (PIF21/69).

References

- [1] N. Epstein, J. Grace, *Handbook of Powder Science & Technology*, Springer, US, 1997, pp. 532–567.
- [2] X. Sukunza, A. Pablos, M. Tellabide, I. Estiati, F.B. Freire, R. Aguado, M. Olazar, A model for predicting the performance of a batch fountain confined spouted bed dryer at low and moderate temperatures, *Powder Technol.* (2022) 117506, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2022.117506>.
- [3] X. Sukunza, A. Pablos, R. Aguado, J. Vicente, H. Altzibar, M. Olazar, Continuous drying of fine and ultrafine sands in a fountain confined conical spouted bed, *Powder Technol.* 388 (2021) 371–379, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2021.117506>.
- [4] A. Pablos, R. Aguado, J. Vicente, H. Altzibar, J. Bilbao, M. Olazar, Effect of operating conditions on the drying of fine and ultrafine sand in a fountain confined conical spouted bed, *Dry. Technol.* 38 (11) (2020) 1446–1461, <https://doi.org/10.1080/07373937.2019.1645684>.
- [5] L. Guo, G. Wang, F. Zhang, P. Wan, Z. Zhu, J. Lin, Effect of temperature on the minimum spouting velocity of heavy particles in conical spouted bed used for nuclear fuel coating, *Exp. Thermal Fluid Sci.* 144 (2023) 110876.
- [6] T. Al-Juwaya, N. Ali, M. Al-Dahhan, Experimental validation of the mechanistic scale-up methodology of gas–solid spouted beds using radioactive particle tracking (RPT), *Ann. Nucl. Energy* 181 (2023) 109559.
- [7] P.K. Mollick, R. Venugopalan, M. Roy, P.T. Rao, D. Sathiyamoorthy, P. Sengupta, G. Sharma, C.B. Basak, J.K. Chakravarty, Deposition of diversely textured buffer pyrolytic carbon layer in TRISO coated particle by controlled manipulation of spouted bed hydrodynamics, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 128 (2015) 44–53, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2015.01.065>.
- [8] M.A. Andrey, Chemical vapor deposition from metal (Cr, Mo, W) carbonyls in a conical spouted bed vacuum reactor with a downflow reactant feeding, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 260 (2022) 117916.
- [9] S. Orozco, L. Santamaria, M. Artetxe, J. Alvarez, J. Bilbao, M. Olazar, G. Lopez, Influence of oxidative conditions on the deactivation of an equilibrium FCC catalyst in the fast pyrolysis of HDPE in a conical spouted bed reactor, *Chem. Eng. J.* 472 (2023) 144947.
- [10] M. Cortazar, G. Lopez, J. Alvarez, M. Amutio, J. Bilbao, M. Olazar, Behaviour of primary catalysts in the biomass steam gasification in a fountain confined spouted bed, *Fuel* 253 (2019) 1446–1456, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2019.05.094>.
- [11] G. Lopez, M. Cortazar, J. Alvarez, M. Amutio, J. Bilbao, M. Olazar, Assessment of a conical spouted with an enhanced fountain bed for biomass gasification, *Fuel* 203 (2017) 825–831, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2017.05.014>.
- [12] L. Qin, J. Han, B. Zhao, Y. Wang, W. Chen, F. Xing, Thermal degradation of medical plastic waste by in-situ FTIR, TG-MS and TG-GC/MS coupled analyses, *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis* 136 (2018) 132–145, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2018.10.012>.
- [13] G. Elordi, M. Olazar, G. Lopez, M. Artetxe, J. Bilbao, Continuous polyolefin cracking on an HZSM-5 zeolite catalyst in a conical spouted bed reactor, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 50 (2011) 6061–6070, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie2002999>.
- [14] S. Orozco, J. Alvarez, G. Lopez, M. Artetxe, J. Bilbao, M. Olazar, Pyrolysis of plastic wastes in a fountain confined conical spouted bed reactor: determination of stable operating conditions, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 229 (2021) 113768, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2020.113768>.
- [15] R. Raman, P.K. Mollick, P.S. Goswami, Computational fluid dynamic-discrete element method studies on dynamics and segregation in spouted bed with Polydispersed particles, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 61 (2022) 9474–9488.
- [16] R. Raman, P.K. Mollick, P.S. Goswami, Numerical studies on particle dynamics in a spouted bed, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 61 (2022) 894–913.
- [17] P.K. Mollick, A.B. Pandit, T. Bhattacharya, P.K. Vijayan, A novel Design of Draft Tube to enhance fluid throughput from spout to annulus in spouted bed, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 59 (2020) 3229–3237, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.9b04035>.
- [18] P.K. Mollick, A.B. Pandit, P.K. Vijayan, Critical assessment of performance of a draft tube configured in a spouted bed for various fluid- particle properties, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 58 (2019) 19670–19680, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.9b04032>.
- [19] P.K. Mollick, A.B. Pandit, P.K. Vijayan, Parameters affecting efficient solid circulation rate in draft tube spouted bed, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 57 (2018) 8605–8611, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.8b01691>.
- [20] P.K. Mollick, D. Sathiyamoorthy, Assessment of stability of spouted bed using pressure fluctuation analysis, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 51 (37) (2012) 12117–12125.
- [21] P.K. Mollick, D. Sathiyamoorthy, P.T. Rao, V.G. Rao, Modeling of chemical vapor deposition of pyrolytic carbon in a gas spouted bed reactor, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 50 (2011) 13313–13321, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie2009636>.
- [22] D. Sathiyamoorthy, V.G. Rao, P.T. Rao, P.K. Mollick, Development of pyrolytic carbon coated zirconia pebbles in a high temperature spouted bed, *Ind. J. Eng. Mater. Sci.* 17 (2010) 349–352.
- [23] M. Liu, Y. Shao, B. Liu, Pressure analysis in the fabrication process of TRISO UO₂-coated fuel particle, *Nucl. Eng. Des.* 250 (2012) 277–283.
- [24] E. L'opez-Honorato, P.J. Meadows, P. Xiao, G. Marsh, T.J. Abram, Structure and mechanical properties of pyrolytic carbon produced by fluidized bed chemical vapor deposition, *Nucl. Eng. Des.* 238 (2008) 3121–3128.
- [25] D. Sathiyamoorthy, V. Govardhana Rao, P.T. Rao, P.K. Mollick, Development of pyrolytic carbon coated zirconia pebbles in a high temperature spouted bed, *Ind. J. Eng. Mater. Sci.* 17 (2010) 349–352.
- [26] Kaushik Sanyal, Dhara Sangita, S. Sanjay Kumar, N.L. Misra, P.K. Mollick, P.T. Rao, R. Venugopalan, Rajesh V. Pai, N. Kumar, S.K. Mukerjee, J.K. Chakravarty, S. K. Aggarwal, Application of TXRF for burn leach test of TRISO coated UO₂ particles, *J. Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.* 302 (2014) 1357–1361.
- [27] W. Zhong, X. Chen, J.R. Grace, N. Epstein, B. Jin, Intelligent prediction of minimum spouting velocity of spouted bed by back propagation neural, *Powder Technol.* 247 (2013) 197–203.
- [28] M. Olazar, G. López, H. Altzibar, R. Aguado, J. Bilbao, Minimum spouting velocity under vacuum and high temperature in conical spouted beds, *Can. J. Chem. Eng.* 87 (4) (2009) 541–546.
- [29] M. Olazar, R. Aguado, M.J. San José, S. Alvarez, J. Bilbao, Minimum spouting velocity for the pyrolysis of scrap tyres with sand in conical spouted beds, *Powder Technol.* 165 (3) (2006) 128–132.
- [30] P.L.S. Neto, F.O. Cunha, J.T. Freire, The influence of paste feed on the minimum spouting velocity, *Braz. J. Chem. Eng.* 18 (3) (2001) 243–251.
- [31] A. Kmieć, The minimum spouting velocity in conical beds, *Can. J. Chem. Eng.* 62 (4) (1984) 571.
- [32] A. Kmieć, The minimum spouting velocity in conical beds, *Can. J. Chem. Eng.* 61 (3) (1983) 274–280.
- [33] S. Golsan, R. Zarghami, N. Mostoufi, A hybrid deterministic–stochastic model for spouted beds, *Particuology* 36 (2018) 139–148.
- [34] M. Tsvik, M. Nabiev, N. Rizaev, K. Merenkov, V. Vyzgo, The velocity for external spouting in the combined process for production of granulated fertilizers, *Uzb. Khim. Zh.* 11 (1967) 50–59.
- [35] S.C.S. Rocha, O.P. Taranto, G.E. Ayub, Aerodynamics and heat transfer during coating of tablets in two-dimensional spouted bed 73 (3) (1995) 308–312.
- [36] M. Choi, A. Meisen, Hydrodynamics of shallow, conical spouted beds, *Can. J. Chem. Eng.* 70 (1992) 916–924, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cjce.5450700513>.
- [37] S.H. Hosseini, M.J. Rezaei, M. Bag-Mohammadi, M. Karami, M.A. Moradkhani, M. Panahi, M. Olazar, Estimation of the minimum spouting velocity in shallow spouted beds by intelligent approaches: study of fine and coarse particles, *Powder Technol.* 354 (2019) 456–465, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2019.06.025>.
- [38] M.A. Moradkhani, S.H. Hosseini, M. Olazar, H. Altzibar, M. Valizadeh, Estimation of the minimum spouting velocity and pressure drop in open-sided draft tube spouted beds using genetic programming, *Powder Technol.* 387 (2021) 363–372, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2021.04.049>.
- [39] Mohammad Amin Moradkhani, Seyyed Hossein Hosseini, Mojtaba Karami, Martin Olazar, F. Saldarriaga Juan, Applying conventional and intelligent approaches to model the minimum spouting velocity of vegetable biomasses in conical spouted beds, *Powder Technol.* 418 (2023) 118300, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2023.118300>.
- [40] Seyyed Hossein Hosseini, Mohammad Amin Moradkhani, Mojtaba Rasteh, Masoud Rahimi, New smart models for minimum fluidization velocity forecasting in the tapered fluidized beds based on particle size distribution, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 60 (42) (2021) 15289–15300, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.1c02682>.
- [41] S.H. Hosseini, M.J. Rezaei, M. Bag-Mohammadi, M. Karami, M.A. Moradkhani, M. Panahi, M. Olazar, Estimation of the minimum spouting velocity in shallow spouted beds by intelligent approaches: study of fine and coarse particles, *Powder Technol.* 354 (2019) 456–465, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2019.06.025>.
- [42] M. Karimi, B. Vaferi, S.H. Hosseini, M. Olazar, S. Rashidi, Smart computing approach for design and scale-up of conical spouted beds with open-sided draft tubes, *Particuology* (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.partic.2020.09.003>.
- [43] W. Zhong, X. Chen, J.R. Grace, N. Epstein, B. Jin, Intelligent prediction of minimum spouting velocity of spouted bed by back propagation neural, *Powder Technol.* 247 (2013) 197–203.